

SI Table 1. Enzymes, NCBI Accessions, Genome IDs, alignment, taxonomic diversity, and ML tree model for query sequences.

Enzyme Name	Accession	Genome ID	Alignment Length	# Taxa	BIC
malate dehydrogenase	WP_012498653	CP001100.1	318	242	LG+R6
fumarate hydratase	WP_012500396	CP001100.1	480	250	LG+R8
fumarate hydratase	WP_010932514	AE006470.1	565	242	LG+R7
fumarate reductase	WP_012498718	CP001100.1	448	248	LG+R8
succinyl-CoA synthetase	WP_012500801	CP001100.1	426	248	LG+R7
2-oxoglutarate:ferredoxin oxidoreductase, alpha subunit	WP_012500035	CP001100.1	657	243	LG+R7
isocitrate dehydrogenase	ACF14612	CP001100.1	356	232	LG+R8
isocitrate dehydrogenase	WP_010932043	AE006470.1	765	250	LG+F+R7
aconitate hydratase	WP_012500984	CP001100.1	775	249	LG+F+R8
aconitate hydratase	WP_010932230	AE006470.1	889	250	LG+F+R7
ATP citrate lyase alpha subunit	WP_012501083	CP001100.1	658	247	LG+R7
ATP citrate lyase beta subunit	WP_012501083	CP001100.1	443	287	LG+R7
pyruvate:ferredoxin oxidoreductase	WP_012499296	CP001100.1	1357	247	LG+R6

SI Figure 1: Maximum likelihood (ML) tree of ATP citrate lyase beta subunit homologs. (A) midpoint-rooted tree with collapsed clades labeled with taxonomic group names. (B) Higher resolution tree showing crown Chlorobiales and closely related sequences in Nitrospira/Nitrospirinae. Support values indicate approximate likelihood ratio test (aLRT)/ bootstrap (100 replicates). Major clades with bootstrap (BS) support are labeled with respective values. Color bars to the right of the tree indicate autotrophic (green), heterotrophic (orange), or undetermined (white) carbon metabolisms.

SI Figure 2: Protein Structural map of *Chlorobium Limicola* ATP Citrate Lyase enzyme (cite published structure here). Structural and labeled functional regions are colored corresponding to bars above sequence alignments. The amino acid alignment includes sequences from *C.thalassium*, *C.limicola*, *Chlorobium* sp.445.

SI Figure 3: Bayesian Inference (BI) consensus trees of ATP citrate lyase alpha (A, C) and beta (B, D) subunit homologs. Trees depicted without (A, B) and with (C, D) Nitrospinae metagenomic sequences from He et. al., 2020 included in the alignment depicted with arrow. Collapsed clades labeled with taxonomic group names. Support values show consensus posterior probabilities.